

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin
Volume 3, Nomor 2, February 2025, P. 109-117
 E-ISSN: [2986-6340](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851006)
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 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851006>

Posey's Selflessness In Her Altruism as Indicated In Mitch Albom's *for One More Day*

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Abstract

This paper explores the concept of selflessness in altruism, as demonstrated by Posey, the mother in Mitch Albom's For One More Day. Through qualitative analysis, the study examines how Posey's actions reflect altruistic behavior, focusing on her unwavering support and sacrifice for her son, Charley. The study investigates instances when Posey consistently puts her son's needs above her own, even at the expense of her own personal interests. By analyzing specific moments in the novel, the study highlights Posey's selflessness as an embodiment of altruistic love, demonstrating how her actions contribute to the emotional well-being and healing of her family. The analysis concludes that Posey's selflessness is a profound representation of unconditional maternal love.

Keywords: *Altruism, For One More Day, Mitch Albom, Selflessness.*

INTRODUCTION

In this society, people are willing to sacrifice for the sake of others, like being willing to save someone who almost have an accident and endanger their own life. This kind of phenomenon is called altruism. Altruism refers to the selfless concern for the well-being of others (Sharma, 2024). Altruism explores the motivations and mechanisms behind selfless behavior where an individual act for the benefit of others at a potential cost to themselves. This term used as the opposite of egoism. (Bhuvana, et al., 2021). In many instances, altruism reflects the fact that the altruist genuinely values the welfare of the beneficiary, such that they intrinsically want to improve their well-being (Rhoads & Marsh, 2023).

Altruism, according to Ricard, is a sincere desire to help others without thinking. Altruism requires a motivation: an instinctive reflex or automatic behavior cannot be qualified as either altruistic or selfish, whatever the beneficial or harmful consequences may be. The difference between altruism and selfishness is qualitative: it is the quality of our motivation and not its intensity that determines its altruistic nature. about one's own needs. He underlines that developing an ongoing mind set of caring and compassion is more important than simply performing random acts of kindness. (Ricard, 2015).

Well-being condition has been defined as the combination of feeling good and functioning well; the experience of positive emotions such as happiness and contentment as well as the development of one's potential, having some control over one's life, having a sense of purpose, and experiencing positive relationships (Ruggeri, et al., 2020; Huppert, 2014). It includes emotional stability, security, and general life happiness in addition to physical and mental health (Hupert & Cooper, 2009). Selfless, on the other hand, is regularly placing the needs or wishes of others before themselves and behaving without regard for one's own aims or gains. Selfless in altruism suggests that a person acts out of a desire to assist others rather than out of any hope of earn recognition, or personal benefit (Batson, 2011).

Through one of Mitch Albom's famous work *For One More Day* that tells a former professional baseball player, Charley Benetto who has reached the lowest point of his life make a decision to take his own life following a bad marriage life, a tense connection with his only daughter, and his battle with drinking alcohol. But during a near-death encounter, he is granted the unique chance to spend one more day with his mother Posey, who passed away. Charley spends the day thinking back on his mistakes and unsolved problems, especially his tense connection with his mother. Despite his selfishness and misconceptions, Posey had always been a selfless presence in his life,

doing all to care for him. As they get back in touch, Posey tells Charley about the sacrifices she made for him, and he realizes the extent of her love and the significance of her altruistic deeds. As Charley learns new lessons about life, forgiveness, and the power of love, this day turns into a journey of healing and redemption.

METHOD

This research is explored through a qualitative method that examines certain concepts and textual data. The researchers try to analyze how the novel *Meet You in the Middle* illustrates the selflessness concept in altruism of the main characters by focusing the research on the mother and son relationship between Posey and Charley Benetto. The aim of this research is to find out the benefits behind the main characters using selflessness in altruism through their relationships where she demonstrates selflessness by repeatedly forgiving his shortcomings and continuing to provide unconditional guidance and love. By taking a close reading of the entire novel and the dialogues between the main characters. It also provides quotations from the novel and the sources that support the analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Posey's Altruism in Mitch Albom's *For One More Day*

Mitch Albom's novel tells about a mom named Posey who does altruistic actions. Posey Benetto's altruism life is depicted in the whole novel with sacrifice and selflessness. She refuses help from Charley's father to maintain her independence after her husband's left him. Posey chooses to earn money by working in multiple places to provide her children with love, comfort, and security, despite her own emotional difficulties. To protect her children from suffering, she always provides a safe and supportive environment and hides her personal pain. The proof of Posey's selflessness is stated in the quotation as follows:

Data 1

The truth is, there is no line. There's only your life, how you mess it up, and who is there to save you. (Chapter 1, Page 3)

From Charley's point of view, he messes his life and his mom is there to save him. It is because he could not be a good father, being an alcoholic person, and also fails to be a good son. Posey is the person who never thinks twice to help her children in every situation even when her children fail (Albom, 2006). Posey's unwavering support, despite Charley's shortcomings, highlights her role as a source of unconditional love and constant forgiveness, demonstrating her empathetic nature by always being there to help him rebuild his life, despite his past mistakes.

Data 2

I saw the other mothers kissing their kids and walking away. I must have started crying. "What's the matter?" my mother asked. "Don't go." "I'll be here when you come out." "No." "It's OK. I'll be here." "What if I can't find you?" "You will." "What if I lose you?" "You can't lose your mother, Charley." (Chapter 1, Page 27)

It is the first day of Charley's kindergarten, Charley sees other mothers kiss their kids and walk away and he starts to feel anxious. Posey is trying to calm him down by making sure that he will not lose his mother (Albom, 2006). This shows the closeness between Posey and Charley. Posey also does not want Charley to be separated from her because that is a mother's duty.

Data 3

...she'd had to drop out of school to work during the war. She earned her high school diploma at night, and did nursing school after that. (Chapter 1, Page 32)

Charley talks about Posey's past. She has to drop out of school, she earns her high school diploma at night and she does nursing school after. It shows how hardworking since she is young and also how complicated Posey's life is (Albom, 2006). She is not only surviving, but she is able to do a lot of things as well. She seems to have many different identities.

Data 4

She loved me coming and going, at my worst and at my best. She had a bottomless well of love for me. (Chapter 2, Page 33)

Charley talks about how bottomless of his mom's love for him. Like, Charley is still forgiven by Posey even though he drops out of college and Posey still accepts him even though he ultimately

chooses baseball over school (Albom, 2006). Not only just accepting, but also later on accompanying Charley even if he is wrong.

Data 5

...I made lists of Times My Mother Stood Up for Me and Times I Did Not Stand Up for My Mother. It was sad, the imbalance of it all. (Chapter 2, Page 33)

It reveals Charley's deep regret and guilt as he reflects on his relationship with his mother. He acknowledges the difference between the countless hours of support his mother gives him and the fewer times he stands up for her (Albom, 2006). This imbalance highlights his feelings of shame for not returning her love and protection.

Data 6

"Dad isn't going to live here anymore." (Chapter 2, Page 57)

Posey indirectly says that they are divorced. Her two children have to get used to not expecting a father in their home. Indirectly, Posey will become the full head of the family (Albom, 2006). This situation forces Posey to take on both parental roles, providing emotional and practical support for her children while dealing with the challenges of being a single parent.

Data 7

"You could pay more attention, Posey! Those people at the hospital aren't the only ones who matter!" (Chapter 2, Page 58)

Charley talks about how their parents argue. It shows that Posey prioritizes patients as same as she does to her family. Charley's father wants Posey to stay home, but Posey has the will and ability to take care of others (Albom, 2006). On the other hand, Posey could balance between work and her children. She could take care of her children very well.

Data 8

I don't know what it is about food your mother makes for you, especially when it's something that anyone can make—pancakes, meat loaf, tuna salad—but it carries a certain taste of memory. My mother used to put chives in her scrambled eggs—"the little green things" I called them—and here they were again. (Chapter 2, Page 61)

Charley is eating his mother's food. It is just a simple food that anyone can make, but mother's food carries a certain of memory. It reflects the emotional connection between food and memories of loved ones, especially a mother (Albom, 2006). Even a simple dish, such as scrambled eggs, has sentimental value because it is associated with moments of love and comfort from the mother.

Data 9

But if we were showed more kindness, my mother was not. (Chapter 2, Page 63)

Charley and Roberta are showing more kindness by the neighborhood after their parents split up but it is the opposite for their mom, Posey (Albom, 2006). Her unspoken sacrifices and hard work for them do not receive the same level of kindness or appreciation she deserves. Despite this, Posey continues to carry out her role as a mother with love and dedication, without complaining or expecting anything in return from those around her.

Data 10

It fell on my mother, mostly because she was still around. (Chapter 2, Page 64)

People did not get divorced back then. Their neighborhood blame Posey because she is still around. This implies that Charley's mother bears the burden and responsibility simply because she is present, while Len, is absent (Albom, 2006). This highlights how Posey is left to handle everything, not because she is the best suited for it, but because she stays while he does not.

Data 11

...Len was gone and Posey was there to be judged. (Chapter 2, Page 64)

Nobody knows what happens between Posey and Len. Len is gone after they split up but Posey is still around to be judged by the neighbors (Albom, 2006). While Len's departure frees him from responsibility, Posey must face the consequences and judgment from society, which could cause a disorder in their families. In the absence of one parent, the remaining parent is often the target of blame or criticism, even when they are not at fault.

Data 12

"I couldn't imagine a life without children. Once, I even... Wait. Let's see." (Chapter 2, Page 72)

Posey reflects on her deep connection to motherhood and the importance of having children in her life. This means that motherhood is a major part of her identity. She cannot imagine her life without it, which shows the sacrifice or emotional burden she carries as a mother (Albom, 2006). This highlights how important being a mother is to Posey's life purpose, further emphasizing the depth of her love and commitment to her children.

Data 13

“So,” she said, moving away, “now you know how badly someone wanted you, Charley. Children forget that sometimes. They think of themselves as a burden instead of a wish granted.” (Chapter 2, Page 73)

Posey shows Charley that there is a tree that she carves back then, she prays for a child. She tells Charley that he is a wish granted instead a burden. Here Posey emphasizes that children often forget that how much their parents want them (Albom, 2006). It is a contradictive idea that children often feeling like a burden instead of a wish grants or the cherish parts of their parents' live. Like many children, he may have lost sight of the love and desire that bring him into the world. That is why his mother wants him to remember how much he is appreciated.

Data 14

MAYBE YOU'RE WONDERING how my mother came to be a hairdresser. As I mentioned, she had been a nurse, and she truly loved being a nurse. She had that deep well of patience to carefully dress bandages, draw blood, and answer endless worried questions with upbeat reassurances. The male patients liked having someone young and pretty around. And the female patients were grateful when she brushed out their hair or helped them put on lipstick. I doubt it was protocol back then, but my mother applied makeup to more than a few occupants of our county hospital. She believed it made them feel better. That was the point of a hospital stay, wasn't it? “You're not supposed to go there and rot,” she would say. (Chapter 2, Page 81)

Charley reflects on how her mother, Posey, transitions from being a nurse to a person who works in beauty Posey has been a nurse because she has a deep well of patience, draws blood, and answers endless worried questions (Albom, 2006). This highlights her caring and compassionate nature, as well as her belief in the importance of maintaining emotional and psychological dignity and beauty, even in a hospital setting. Her actions—such as applying makeup to patients—are not just about physical care but also about uplifting the spirit. This reflects her deep commitment to making others feel better, both as a nurse and later as a person who works in beauty.

Data 15

...and with my father out of the picture, my mother tried to work as many shifts as she could... (Chapter 2, Page 82)

Charley recalls how her mother, Posey, takes on extra work after his father leaves. This shows her resilience and determination to provide for her family despite being a single parent. (Albom, 2006) By working multiple shifts, she tries to compensate for his father's absence, showing her dedication and sacrifice in ensuring the well-being of her children.

Data 16

“Yes, sweetie, something like that.” (Chapter 2, Page 83)

Posey gets fired and picks up her kids from school. Roberta asks if the hospital let her out of work early, and Posey says yes instead of telling her the truth (Albom, 2006). This reflects her gentle and compassionate approach. She may simplify more complex or painful explanations for Roberta, offering comfort and reassurance rather than digging into difficult details.

Data 17

She sniffed. She looked in the rearview mirror and wiped the black from around her eyes. “How about some ice cream?” she said. “Yeah! Yeah!” my sister said. “I have practice,” I said. “Oh, why don't you skip the practice, OK?” (Chapter 2, Page 83)

Posey tries to cheer up her children by suggesting ice cream, despite her own emotional state, as indicated by wiping off the black makeup around her eyes—presumably from crying. Charley's reluctance to skip practice contrasts with her mother's desire to enjoy small moments of joy and togetherness (Albom, 2006). The context suggests Posey's attempt to protect her children from her sadness and create positive memories, even during difficult times, especially when Charley's response reflects the tension between her responsibilities and her mother's need for connection.

Data 18

Her reward for standing up for herself was the suggestion that “it isn’t going to work out anymore.” (Chapter 2, Page 84)

Posey has complained about inappropriate behavior from senior members of the staff, and she gets fired for standing up for herself (Albom, 2006). This highlights the painful reality that taking a stand for oneself does not always lead to a positive outcome, and it underscores the emotional toll Posey experiences from being pushed aside. Although Posey is brave enough to stand up for herself, the reality is that she has to endure unfair consequences, which only ruin her feelings of disappointment and hurt from the treatment she received.

Data 19

...her bedroom door is closed and I think I hear her crying. (Chapter 2, Page 86)

Posey fights with Charley. He hears his mother, Posey, crying behind her closed bedroom door, which symbolizes her personal pain and vulnerability (Albom, 2006). The closed door shows the separation between her emotional struggles and her family, suggesting that although she appears strong and tries to protect her children, she is suffering from deep sadness in solitude. It reveals a hidden aspect of her character, suggesting that she too faces moments of emotional breakdown away from the eyes of others.

Data 20

My mother eases out the door. “Stay here,” she whispers. (Chapter 2, Page 92)

Posey sacrifices herself by telling their children to stay in the room while she is going out of the room to check if there is a robber in the house. This moment shows the mother’s caring and protective attitude (Albom, 2006). By telling Charley to stay, she tries to protect him from something difficult or painful. It also reflects the closeness and gentle way she manages her relationship with her son, even in times of tension or transition.

The Significance of Idea behind Altruism and Selflessness

Behavior is normally described as altruistic when it is motivated by a desire to benefit someone other than oneself for that person’s sake (Kraut, 2020). Altruism define as the act that benefits other person without expecting anything in return (Radovanović, 2019). A French term derived from the word ‘autrui’ was first coined by a French philosopher and writer Auguste Comte in 1852. Altruism refers to a selfless behavior of human being without considering much about the consequences of such behavior (Mishra & Singhal, 2022). This contrasts with the other forms of social behavior: selfish, mutually beneficial and spiteful (Dawkins, 1976).

Selflessness is when someone is altruistic, they are putting the needs, interests, and desires of others above their own. Selfless people act altruistically by putting aside their own interests or benefits and acting primarily with the intention of helping others, sometimes at personal cost. Selflessness would be primarily guided by the principle of “harmony”, in the sense that the individual is facing a harmonious adjustment with the different elements of the environment, including others and the different forms of life (Leary, et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017).

This trait captures the essence of altruism, which is the drive to behave in the best possible way for others without considering own benefit or recognition. Altruism comes from selflessness, which emphasizes that the person is prepared to give up time, resources, or well-being for the benefit of others without expecting compensation or recognition in return. Ignoring one's own issues in order to show more care for others means putting one's own needs, wants, or worries aside in order to help or encourage another person.

Posey’s Selflessness in Mitch Albom’s *For One More Day*

This section discusses how Posey’s selflessness in *For One More Day* reveals factors that lead to altruism. These aspects are further explained below:

In **Data 1**, Posey's actions reflect selflessness. Charley feels his life is in chaos and falling apart, but his mother, Posey, is always there to save him. Although Charley feels like a failure as a father and son, Posey never hesitates to help her children in any situation, even when they fail. This shows that Posey puts Charley's needs and well-being above his own, without expecting reward or recognition. Posey's actions illustrate the principle of harmony, where she adapts herself to his

surroundings, including Charley, and acts primarily with the intention of helping, even though there may be personal costs (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017).

In **Data 2**, Posey's actions reflect the trait of selflessness. When Charley feels anxious on the first day of kindergarten, Posey goes out of her way to reassure him that she will be there and that Charley will not lose her mother. Posey put aside her own interests and feelings, completely prioritizing Charley's emotional needs at that moment. Her actions demonstrate that she acts selflessly, putting her children's well-being above all else, without expecting reward or recognition (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This attitude reflects the essence of selflessness, which is to put aside one's own interests for the good of others, in this case, providing a sense of security and comfort for Charley.

In **Data 3**, Posey's actions reflect selflessness. She had to leave school to work during the war, but still worked hard to get her high school diploma at night and go to nursing school. Her sacrifice shows that Posey is willing to put aside her own interests to help others (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). Despite her difficult life, she continues to work hard for the good of others, showing an altruistic nature without expecting anything in return.

In **Data 4**, Posey's actions in this data demonstrate selflessness. Even though Charley makes disappointing decisions such as dropping out of college and choosing baseball over education, Posey still loves and supports him unconditionally. Not only she accepts Charley for who he is, but she also supports him and forgives him, even when he makes mistakes (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This shows that Posey put aside her feelings or interests for the sake of her child's happiness and well-being, an act that is completely altruistic and demonstrates selflessness by putting Charley's needs first without expecting any reward or recognition.

In **Data 5**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. Although Charley is aware of the imbalance between the amount of support his mother gives him and the little opportunity for him to reciprocate, Posey continues to provide unconditional love and protection. He is always there for Charley without expecting anything in return or recognition, demonstrating an altruistic attitude by putting his own needs aside for the sake of his son (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This reflects an act of selflessness where Posey continues to put Charley's happiness before her own desires.

In **Data 6**, what Posey does reflect selflessness because she is willing to take full responsibility for her family after the divorce. Although it may have been difficult for Posey to live as a single parent, she does not dwell on her personal difficulties, but focuses on the well-being of her children (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). She puts aside her own needs and tries to provide emotional and practical support for them.

In **Data 7**, what Posey does reflect selflessness because she is able to balance her professional responsibilities as a nurse in the hospital and her obligations as a mother. Although her husband felt that Posey does not pay enough attention to her family, Posey still dedicates her life to caring for others, including her patients (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This shows that she put the needs of others above her own interests. Posey's actions are in line with the principle of harmony in the explanation of selflessness, where she adjusts to various responsibilities without seeking recognition or appreciation, only focusing on helping others.

In **Data 8**, what Posey does shows selflessness because even though the food she makes is simple and could be made by anyone, she makes it with love for her children. Posey's actions in preparing this food reflect how she always tries to meet Charley's emotional needs, even through small things like cooking. By paying attention to details like the "little green things" in the omelet, Posey shows that she cares about her child's happiness and comfort without expecting anything in return (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This is in line with the concept of selflessness, which is putting the needs of others before your own needs, especially in creating loving memories.

In **Data 9**, Posey's actions reflect selflessness, because, although she works hard and sacrifices for her children after the divorce, she does not receive the same appreciation or kindness from her environment. Posey continues to carry out her mother's duties with full responsibility without expecting any reward or recognition from others (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This is in line with the element of selflessness because she prioritizes the interests of her children over her own, ignoring the injustices she experienced to protect them. This trait shows that she is ready to do whatever it takes to help others, even if it does not produce the results she wants.

In **Data 10**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. She remains alive and fully responsible after the divorce, even though those around her only blame her for being there. Even when she is unfairly blamed, Posey bears the burden without complaint. This is in line with the element of independence in that she leaves her personal interests behind and faces difficult situations for her children without seeking support or recognition (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). She demonstrates a selfless commitment to caring for her family without expecting any reward or recognition.

In **Data 11**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. She remains loyal to her family even though she is abandoned by Len and must face the judgment of her community. Although she is not wrong, Posey faces criticism and judgment from society without running away from her responsibilities. This shows an aspect of independence, where Posey leaves her personal desires behind and is willing to accept pressure and negative judgment to take care of her family (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). Even though the consequences are severe, she remains present and responsible, demonstrating selfless actions.

In **Data 12**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. She puts her children's interests before her own. Posey notes the role of motherhood in her life in the data, to the point that she cannot imagine life without her children. This shows that Posey has become her primary identity as a mother, and she is ready to take on the responsibilities and feelings that come with that role. Posey's actions demonstrate how she is willing to sacrifice her own needs for her children without expecting recognition or reward (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). Here, selflessness is characterized by harmony between herself and those she loves; Posey sacrifices herself for the sake of her children.

In **Data 13**, Posey's actions in this data reflect selflessness. She shows Charley that he is not a burden, but rather a wish come true. Posey emphasizes how valuable Charley is as her child, even though children often feel like burdens (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This shows that Posey is putting aside her own feelings and focusing on her child's emotional needs, which fits the element of selflessness where someone makes sacrifices for the benefit of others without expecting anything in return.

In **Data 14**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. In addition to caring for patients physically, Posey helps them feel better with small things like doing their hair or putting on makeup. She does this to make the patient feel better, not because she is a nurse. Posey puts aside her own interests to provide emotional and psychological comfort for the patient without expecting anything in return, reflecting an element of selflessness in this action (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This is in line with the definition of selflessness, which emphasizes sacrifice for the benefit of others.

In **Data 15**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. She takes on the dual role of a single parent after Charley's father leaves. By working as many shifts as possible, Posey sacrifices her own time and energy to provide for her family. This is a form of sacrifice where she places the interests and well-being of her children above her own needs (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). Posey shows that she is willing to give her time without expecting anything in return, just to ensure the well-being of her family.

In **Data 16**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. Posey chooses not to tell Roberta that she was fired. Posey sacrifices her own emotions by saying "Yes, sweetie, something like that" to prevent her child from being sad or worried. This shows how she puts her children's interests before her own (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). She is willing to endure personal pain or problems just to provide comfort and protection for her children, without expecting recognition.

In **Data 17**, Posey's actions show selflessness. Even though she is in an emotional state, as seen from the way she wipes the black makeup around her eyes, she still tries to cheer up her children by taking them out for ice cream. This shows how Posey puts aside her own feelings for the sake of her children's happiness, even when she is facing sadness (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). She tries to create positive moments together and protect her children from knowing how sad she is. She puts her children's needs above her own without expecting any recognition or reward, just to provide happiness and comfort for them.

In **Data 18**, Posey's actions demonstrate selflessness. Although she stands up for herself against the inappropriate behavior of senior staff, she lost her job. This shows that Posey is willing to face severe personal consequences for the sake of maintaining his integrity, which led to his termination. Her sacrifice reflects an element of selflessness, where she does not prioritize her

personal gain, but rather the principles she believes are right, even though it means losing her job (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). She puts aside her personal interests without expecting recognition or compensation, and in this case, she even pays a high price for his courage.

In **Data 19**, Posey's actions show selflessness. Even though she is experiencing deep sadness, she chooses to close herself off and cry behind a closed bedroom door. This reflects her attempt to protect her children from her own emotional burden, even though she is suffering emotionally. She puts aside her own needs and feelings in order to protect the feelings of others, which are her children, so that they do not feel the sadness or worry that she is experiencing (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This sacrifice shows how she tries to maintain harmony in her family even though she has to bear her pain alone.

In **Data 20**, Posey's actions reflect selflessness. She puts her children's safety first by sacrificing herself to ensure their home is safe. By ordering Charley to stay in the room while she goes out to check for a robber, Posey shows that she is putting aside her own safety and comfort in order to protect her children (Leary et al., 2008 in Dambrun, 2017). This shows that she is willing to sacrifice her time, energy, and even her own safety for the well-being of her children, in line with the element of selflessness that emphasizes sacrifice without expecting anything in return. Posey focuses on the needs of her children, trying to protect them from the fears and hardships they may face, even though she herself must face a potentially dangerous situation.

CONCLUSION

For One More Day by Mitch Albom is a novel that explores the sacrifice and selflessness, and ultimate love between mother and son. The main characters of this novel are Posey and Charley Benetto, who had unsolved problems especially the tensed relationship between them felt by Charley. Moreover, this novel illustrates how selflessness in altruism is reflected in Posey's quiet strength and determination to protect and guide her children, even when she herself is facing adversity. As a lesson in the power of love, sacrifice, and resilience, Posey's actions leave a lasting impact on her family, especially Charley. Posey's selfless devotion emphasizes the importance of unconditional love and how far a mother will go for her children.

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